

Short name	Communication and the 'information deficit'	Long name	Public communication about CCUS – is it just a case of information deficit?
Geographical scope	Most research on public perceptions of CCUS focuses on research in European nations (either single countries or comparative) ^{1,2} . North American and East Asian nations are also regularly represented in the research literature.		
Description of how this issue tends to manifest (include footnotes for key references)	<p>[Please see the 'Public Awareness' issue profile first for relevant context.]</p> <p>Scholarly attention to communication of CCUS has been critiqued by some scholars; we discuss three reasons here.</p> <p>First, even in studies that reveal a genuine statistically significant empirical connection suggesting that certain information or messages can lead to, or are associated with, higher acceptance, the magnitude (and therefore real world meaningfulness) of the effect is often small. For example, a shift in acceptance of 0.15 on a 1-5 scale of support/opposition, brought on by a new approach to communicating about CCUS, could be statistically significant, but will mean very little for acceptance of a real project³.</p> <p>Second, although appeals for effective CCUS communication are nearly universal in the research literature, there are also several claims about 'information deficit' – an empirically invalid assumption that people simply lack information and will necessarily change their views when gaining additional knowledge⁴. The actual evidence from the public perception and communication studies shows a broad mix of additional information marginally increasing support for CCUS, decreasing support, or having no effect².</p> <p>Third, even if communication were to increase acceptance, some scholars question whether this should be the goal⁵. Several studies point to communication (and information design) as one step in a public engagement process, but only an incremental stage that follows understanding of perceived risks and benefits⁶, but is then followed by robust and credible public engagement and a transparent decision-making process that reflects the engagement^{7,8}. The relational context matters for any energy project, and CCUS deployment is no exception; for example, the role of trust in social acceptance is discussed in several other issue profiles⁹⁻¹².</p>		
Key examples where this issue manifests (also	A key consideration for any government or industry actor engaged in CCUS governance or project management will be how to approach communication and interactions with local and national publics. The		

based on stakeholder inputs)	social scientific literature provides indications that simple messaging and information provision is likely inadequate and more participatory, detailed, and iterative forms of engagement might be helpful ⁵⁻⁸ .
Other issues this affects	Public support for CCUS, public engagement with CCUS, public awareness of CCUS, trust in government and industry actors
References	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tcvetkov, P., Cherepovitsyn, A., & Fedoseev, S. (2019). Public perception of carbon capture and storage: A state-of-the-art overview. <i>Heliyon</i>, 5(12), e02845. • Selma, L., Seigo, O., Dohle, S., & Siegrist, M. (2014). Public perception of carbon capture and storage (CCS): A review. <i>Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews</i>, 38, 848-863. • Whitmarsh, L., Xenias, D., & Jones, C. R. (2019). Framing effects on public support for carbon capture and storage. <i>Palgrave Communications</i>, 5(1). • Braun, C. (2017). Not in my backyard: CCS sites and public perception of CCS. <i>Risk Analysis</i>, 37(12), 2264-2275. • Leiss, W., & Larkin, P. (2019). Risk communication and public engagement in CCS projects: The foundations of public acceptability. <i>International Journal of Risk Assessment and Management</i>, 22(3-4), 384-403. • Vercelli, S., Anderlucci, J., Memoli, R., Battisti, N., Mabon, L., & Lombardi, S. (2013). Informing people about CCS: a review of social research studies. <i>Energy Procedia</i>, 37, 7464-7473. • Brunsting, S., Pol, M., Mastop, J., Kaiser, M., Zimmer, R., Shackley, S., ... & Rybicki, C. (2013). Social Site Characterisation for CO2 storage operations to inform public engagement in Poland and Scotland. <i>Energy Procedia</i>, 37, 7327-7336. • Coyle, F. J. (2016). 'Best practice' community dialogue: The promise of a small-scale deliberative engagement around the siting of a carbon dioxide capture and storage (CCS) facility. <i>International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control</i>, 45, 233-244. • Broecks, K., Jack, C., Ter Mors, E., Boomsma, C., & Shackley, S. (2021). How do people perceive carbon capture and storage for industrial processes? Examining factors underlying public opinion in the Netherlands and the United Kingdom. <i>Energy Research & Social Science</i>, 81, 102236.

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mabon, L., & Littlecott, C. (2016). Stakeholder and public perceptions of CO₂-EOR in the context of CCS—results from UK focus groups and implications for policy. <i>International journal of greenhouse gas control</i>, 49, 128-137. • Mabon, L., Shackley, S., & Bower-Bir, N. (2014). Perceptions of sub-seabed carbon dioxide storage in Scotland and implications for policy: a qualitative study. <i>Marine Policy</i>, 45, 9-15. • Williams, R., Jack, C., Gamboa, D., & Shackley, S. (2021). Decarbonising steel production using CO₂ Capture and Storage (CCS): Results of focus group discussions in a Welsh steel-making community. <i>International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control</i>, 104, 103218.
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Literature

¹ Tcvetkov, P., Cherepovitsyn, A., & Fedoseev, S. (2019). Public perception of carbon capture and storage: A state-of-the-art overview. *Heliyon*, 5(12), e02845.

² Selma, L., Seigo, O., Dohle, S., & Siegrist, M. (2014). Public perception of carbon capture and storage (CCS): A review. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 38, 848-863.

³ Whitmarsh, L., Xenias, D., & Jones, C. R. (2019). Framing effects on public support for carbon capture and storage. *Palgrave Communications*, 5(1).

⁴ Braun, C. (2017). Not in my backyard: CCS sites and public perception of CCS. *Risk Analysis*, 37(12), 2264-2275.

⁵ Leiss, W., & Larkin, P. (2019). Risk communication and public engagement in CCS projects: The foundations of public acceptability. *International Journal of Risk Assessment and Management*, 22(3-4), 384-403.

⁶ Vercelli, S., Anderlucci, J., Memoli, R., Battisti, N., Mabon, L., & Lombardi, S. (2013). Informing people about CCS: a review of social research studies. *Energy Procedia*, 37, 7464-7473.

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⁸ Coyle, F. J. (2016). 'Best practice' community dialogue: The promise of a small-scale deliberative engagement around the siting of a carbon dioxide capture and storage (CCS) facility. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, 45, 233-244.

⁹ Broecks, K., Jack, C., Ter Mors, E., Boomsma, C., & Shackley, S. (2021). How do people perceive carbon capture and storage for industrial processes? Examining factors underlying public opinion in the Netherlands and the United Kingdom. *Energy Research & Social Science*, 81, 102236.

¹⁰ Mabon, L., & Littlecott, C. (2016). Stakeholder and public perceptions of CO₂-EOR in the context of CCS—results from UK focus groups and implications for policy. *International journal of greenhouse gas control*, 49, 128-137.

¹¹ Mabon, L., Shackley, S., & Bower-Bir, N. (2014). Perceptions of sub-seabed carbon dioxide storage in Scotland and implications for policy: a qualitative study. *Marine Policy*, 45, 9-15.

¹²Williams, R., Jack, C., Gamboa, D., & Shackley, S. (2021). Decarbonising steel production using CO₂ Capture and Storage (CCS): Results of focus group discussions in a Welsh steel-making community. *International Journal of Greenhouse Gas Control*, 104, 103218.